

JOURNAL OF ENGLISH STUDIES

ISSN : 3122-0479

DOI – <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18037891>

Volume 1 No 2 December (2025): Journal of English Studies

<https://joesfudutsinma.com.ng/joes/index.php/one/article/view/40>

joesfudma@gmail.com

**GRAPHOLOGICAL AND PHONO-STYLISTIC HERMENEUTICS OF SELECTED
POEMS IN J.P. CLARK'S 'FULL TIDE'**

Obinna Iroegbu, PhD

Department of English and Literary Studies

Federal University, Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

obinna.iroegbu@fuoye.edu.ng

+2347064366465

&

OmoladeBamigboye, PhD

Department of English and Literary Studies

Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

douglas_e4@yahoo.com; omolade.bamigboye@eksu.edu.ng

+2348038409074

Abstract

This paper undertakes an examination of the nature and import of the graphological and rhyming features deployed in a selection of J.P. Clark's poetry. All the poems examined are selected from the poet's full collection, *Full Tide*. Although the poet has added a few more titles to his collection afterwards, *Full Tide* can be said to duly represent the content and context of Clark's career as a distinguished Nigerian poet. The article employs Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics as theoretical guide. Seventeen poems from the anthology are purposively selected and examined for evident graphological and phonological elements which are indicative of the poet's stylistic and aesthetic inclinations. It is observed that Clark deliberately deploys linguistic patterns suggestive of foregrounded forms which yield to interpretations that are easily connected to the thematic concern of his poems. Such patterns include, but are not limited to, rhyme schemes and graphological stylistic applications such as spacing, lineation and structural deviation that carry artistic concerns that range from civil-military relations, to environmental dilapidation, and cultural identity as well as celebration. These findings validate the assertion that graphological and phono-stylistic features are meaning-inducing concepts that often go beyond aesthetics to engender a reinforcement of thematic interest of poets. It concludes that Clark's exploitation of these stylistic features provide valuable insight into his poetic craft and the broader linguistic creativity characteristic of modern African poetry.

Keywords: J.P. Clark, graphological features, rhyme schemes, *Full Tide*

Introduction

The analysis of poetry as a genre of literature usually involves an attention drawn to the phonological features. This is mainly because poetry, like drama, is by design a type of language use which is written to be recited or verbally enacted. It is primarily a genre that is connected to speech. Although the volume of work to be studied is essentially written, features of speech especially in terms of prosody, versification, rhyme, rhythm, sound symbolism and conscious play on sounds are observable in Clark's poetry. These aforementioned features often constitute what can be harnessed as the style of the writer. In other words, it is the particular application of the aforementioned terms that imbues the writer's work with specificity and distinction which in turn account for stylistic readings.

Style at the level of graphology and phonology, in this case, rhyme scheme, may require extrapolative accounts that evince features that are easily accessible to the least analyst. However, in a deeper assessment, stylistic reading may unearth forms and patterns that might be hardly prognostic. These more or less hidden or embedded forms and patterns are nevertheless quite significant and help to generate a more productive reading of the text involved.

J.P. Clark is one of the most productive and iconic writers in Nigeria. As a contemporary of Wole Soyinka and Chinua Achebe, right from their undergraduate days at the University College, Ibadan, Clark comparatively demonstrated a consistence in the poetic genre than any other form of writing, and more than other writers in his class. Owing to his huge collection of poetry and an appreciable number of dramatic works, Clark has received a proportionally high amount of critical and scholarly attention (Eghagha, 2004). It can easily be said that no major anthology of iconic Nigerian, indeed, African poetry could be deemed complete without a title of

Clark's poem. Beyond the indisputable significance of Clark's contribution to the development of Nigeria literature, his poems offer a typical assessment of the relevance of stylistic choices to thematic inclination. Clark's poetry thus, discovers an array of novel stylistic approaches that contribute to more robust appreciation of poetry as a literary genre.

Literature Review

Observing the lack of interest in the linguistic appraisal of J.P. Clark's work, Eyo (2005) comments that:

most of the critical views (on Clark-Bekederemo) concentrate on the traditional thematic approach to criticism, almost in complete isolation from language; the critics do not approach Clark-Bekederemo's poetry from the perspective of stylistic criticism (22).

Eyo identifies that this lack of linguistic approach to the study of the poet has contributed to the poor understanding of Clark's poetry. Quoting Anozie (1989), he maintains that since poetry is primarily a verbal approach to signification, its appraisal might be "insightful and rewarding if it is approached from a linguistic viewpoint" (23).

Yeibo (2011) is one of the most outstanding scholars in Clark's poetry. Yeibo is not only outstanding with regard to the number of journal articles and chapters in books he has dedicated to Clark's poetry but also with respect to the fact that his adherence to linguistic principles is undeniable. He mostly applies Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics model in most of his analysis. Commenting on the poet's stylistic application of linguistic forms, he observes that:

the poet deploys these lexico-grammatical patterns of language use to relate his

propositions to specific persons, time and place which not only makes the texts experiential and realistic, but also enhances their understanding and interpretation (14).

Yeibo's summation is the type which stems from a proper linguistic account based on empirical evidence as illustrated in the analysis. Thus, the analyst first observes an occurrence and secondly identifies the correlative significance of this observation to the thematic essence of the poem under review

Yerima (2011) comments that:

J.P. Clark wrote at the dawn of a new era in Africa, in which the African consciousness was free to wonder, evolve ideological positions and define and decide the trend of its future and socio-political independence (23 – 24).

Yerima's view is in reference to Clark generally as a writer. He is only trying to situate Clark within the time configuration of African literary writings. In reference to Clark's language, he observes that the essence of J.P. Clark's creative genius is in the writer's "fluid creative complexity". He highlights that "complexity", as indicated, is not that of understanding the poet's language but of the fact that Clark possesses the "ability to flow from one genre to another with ease". Although there are no deliberate attempts to engage in an illustrative account of the features that indicate "fluid creative complexity", Yerima's view here is hinged on a linguistic

stand. We say this because Yerima is trying to point out that in Clark's writing there seems to be a mixture of the descriptive features of an essayist and the metaphoric or symbolic nature of a poet.

Okai (2011), in a similar view as that initially expressed by Yerima, is of the opinion that:

Clark Bekederemo is writing because he
is a writer whose literary career is a
creational marathon whose origin was
tap-rooted in the spirit and times of the
foundation layers of Nigerian literature
(30).

This view is essentially thematic. Although he makes a general reference to Clark as a writer, Okai does not give any insight into the dynamics of the language of the poet. We review him here because we desire to add up to our opinion that Clark belongs to the earliest class of nationalistic African writers. This nationalistic function is also indicated in Okai's conclusion that the works and career of Clark should be placed "within the context of the phenomenon of the impact of the arts on societal development". Okai, like all other scholars reviewed in this section, is, as already stated, essentially concerned with aesthetics and theme. This present research differs significantly in the sense that it offers a corpus-based account of linguistic features extracted and analysed to indicate their stylistic relevance.

Theoretical Framework

Halliday's systemic functional linguistics (SFL) is the major theory adopted for a greater part of this paper. Halliday and Matthiessen (2004) consider language as a peculiar human phenomenon

which involves a network of systems of inter-related contrasts. This conceptualization of language sees it in the light of a system of choices realized in structural relations. They explain that “a system is a set of options with an entry condition, such that exactly one option must be chosen if the entry condition is satisfied” (2004:262). Structural relation implies that the existence or occurrence of one item predisposes the choice or occurrence of either one or another form of the item in a successive or substitutionary capacity.

The SFL, here, offers tools for terms and procedural techniques in analyses. The theory easily yields to context-based justification of linguistic features. Poetry is an expression of language and in use. It a practical demonstration of the artistic and aesthetic value of language as applied by writers. A better appreciation of poetry, therefore, requires the connection of its inherent linguistic forms and feature to the mediate and immediate linguistic context. This is because language is not some cosmetic or artificial construct but a systemic means by which the meaning-generating potentials of textual forms are enacted. McCarthy et al (2010:63) explain that the systemic linguistics is concerned with the “investigation of how language is structured to achieve socio-cultural meanings”. According to them, the grammatical theory does this by “focusing on the analysis of texts, considered in relationship to the social context in which they occur” (63). Commenting on the functionality of the theory, they assert that functional descriptions seek to explain the nature and organization of language according to what it has to do” especially with regard to “describing the relationship of language, text and social life” (62).

Crystal and Davy (1986) identify phonology and graphology as two significant levels of linguistic analysis. Recognizing phonology as that which studies the sound system and graphology as that pertaining to writing, punctuation and related forms, they identify that the

application of the two to stylistics results in the description of “patterns of sound or writing that distinguish, or assist in distinguishing, varieties of English – repetition of segmental sounds in specific distribution, patterns of rhythm, intonation and other non-segmental varia, (as well as) distinctive of use of punctuation, capitalization, spacing, and so on (18). It is their opinion that “stylisticians” should approach any text under examination with various levels of linguistic analysis in mind. However, the common approach to linguistic analysis of literary texts, especially, in this case, Clark, often tends to the lexico-semantic and grammatical levels. Undoubtedly, poetry yields more appreciation and understanding if its analysis incorporates patterns of sound and writing.

Methodology

The study involves seventeen purposefully selected poems of Clark. The poems include, “His Excellency, the Masquerader”, “Olokun”, “Locust hunt” and fourteen others. These poems are selected because they exhibit features indicating special graphological forms and phonostylistics. In terms of analysis, the study thus covers two levels of linguistic analysis, including phonology and graphology. These poems also offer peculiar features which can be better appreciated applying the systemic functional model. In these poems, linguistic features that bear or present significant connection between text and context are examined. Here, graphology and phonology offer semiotic readings and interpretations that justify the poet’s stylistic preferences. This decision is motivated by the recognition that SFL as a functional linguistic model recognizes the role of semantics in arriving at any judgment with respect to the significance of a text.

Analysis and Discussions

The study will involve the extraction of excerpts or whole poems manifesting foregrounded forms indicating special application of graphology and phonology as stylistic features. Essentially, text that indicate pictorial graphology, like “Locust hunt”, “The playwright and the colonel” and “Service”, are presented in full texts. Other forms of stylistically motivated graphology, such as line length and punctuation are presented in excerpts.

Line length

Manipulation of line is the major way by which concretization of poetry can be effected. Thus, it is the careful adjustment of the number of words occurring per line that brings about a noticeable shape which has a suggestive or symbolic and underpinning co-referential relationship with the entire poem. In “His Excellency, the Masquerader” (a poem hereafter to be referred with a simple abbreviation, HETM) which deals with the topic of political representation being compared to a bridge, the line lengths are carefully adjusted to reflect this thematic concern. Consequently, the poem, in shape, is designed like a bridge. The bridge shape offers a clear demarcation between one point and the other. The two points being co-joined in this case are the first and the final (last) line of each of the three-lined stanzas of the poem. As it is presented, the first and second stanzas indicate this line length manipulation for concretization of poetic value as they go:

He serves

To ford between swamp and sand

He serves;

The bridge stands,

All that stone and steel put together

It stands! (HETM, *Full Tide*)

Thus, in talking about a bridge which links two points together, the shape of the poem concretizes and brings into view this function. However, this deliberate concretization is harmonized with the lexico-semantic feature of the text whereby there is an incidence of degenerative transitivity resulting or reflected in the depreciating connotation of semantic reference of the lexical items occurring in the text.

Consecutive degeneration or sequential bathos is likewise reflected in the reduction of the line length to such an extent that it would not be out of place to observe that there appears to be a kind of competition between the middle line and the terminal line of each stanza. This competition goes on to the point that, in the last two stanzas of the poem, there is a considerable comparative reduction in the length of the middle line. This reduction is significant because, it appears that the poem evidently downplays the relevance of the reference who serves as a bridge, hence we have:

In Ojoto

So they worship the masks,

Although in seasons –

The masks!

O take off the masks! And behind?

What wind! What straw! (HETM, *Full Tide*)

Comparative reduction and increase occur with regard to the middle and the final lines of each stanza, respectively. Thus, the last line, as already indicated, begins to increase/grow in length to the extent that there is a noticeable increase in each successive last line till the end of the poem.

In “Olokun”, concretization of theme comes in the form of the last line of each stanza appearing to be a consistent bulwark to the succeeding lines. The last line is lengthier. This significantly relates to the field of discourse and context of situation in which the poet/persona expresses his desire for an intimacy and reliance/dependence on the reference, *Olokun*. Thus, *Olokun* as a reference is symbolically concretized by the last line. This last line is like the foundation.

As tide through weeds of the sea

And wind the tall fern-fronds,

I love to pass my fingers

Through the strands of your hair

Dark as night that screens the naked moon (“Olokun”, *Full Tide*)

Besides being relatively lengthier than any of the preceding lines, the last line has lexicosemantic consistence to the extent that it, in each of the stanzas, contains a direct or indirect reference to Olokun. Thus, in this first line, Olokun’s hair functions in a co-referential capacity to ‘night’ which “screens the naked moon”. Although not in any way suggestively mentioned, Olokun’s face is in direct comparison and co-referential capacity to the moon. This is because as the night whose darkness is comparable to Olokun’s hair “screens the naked moon”, the hair screens her beautiful face. Consequently, subsequent last lines end in Olokun’s co-referential features, thus we have:

Stanza 2 you (Olokun)

Stanza 3 your eyes (Olokun's eyes)

Stanza 4 your breast (Olokun's breast)

Appendage and superposition

In “The locust hunt”, concretization also plays out in the shape of the poem. The poem is so designed such that the section, in this case, the first stanza, which describes “the locusts” being hunted down, appears as an imposing or domineering crown bearing it down on the other sections (the rest two stanzas of the poem). The *locust* being referenced here is a metaphor for the Igbo. Thus, at the beginning of the Nigerian nationhood, the Igbos dominated every facet of the society, be it the military, the academia (an Igbo was the first indigenous VC of a majority of the first generation Universities), the industries, trade & commerce as well as the Civil Service. The dominating Igbos are thus comparable to the locust which usually take over any field in which they are allowed access. In this sense, the locust (as a metaphor of the Igbo) assumes the shape of a crown as the poem illustrates:

“The locust hunt”

Locusts were discovered outside city walls

Locusts were decried in stranger settlements

Locusts were hunted down to women and children

With mortar, machete, with broomsticks and rackets
In shops, in streets, in offices
Locusts were hunted down in courts and convents.

So a royal bull was slain
With all the egrets on his hump
So dog ate dog in a hunt
With a scattering of the pack in the plain
Oh, how many grasshoppers make up
The loss of one elephant?
How many ticks must there be
To eat up one mastiff?

A river under clear skies
Keeps to its channel, but let
The clouds break, let them break
And ripped below are the banks upon the plains
And let them remember on the banks
The fire struck by one spark,
In grasslands or forest,
Lights up a stockpile. (“The locust hunt”, *FullTide*)

It is symbolically significant that the number of lines in the three stanzas differ. The first stanza, which as we said represents the Igbo, is made up of six lines in contrast to the other two stanzas which can be said represent the other two regions. These two stanzas contain nine lines each.

Very much like the shape of “The locust hunt”, “The playwright and the colonels” also presents a similar concretization of text in which a reference is symbolically dominated. “The playwright and colonels” is expressively and without apology a direct retaliatory attack on Wole Soyinka. The poem illustrates how stanza length and line/stanza position can be imbued with correlating and symbolic connection with regard to the context of situation or field of discourse.

“The playwright and the colonels (to Wole Soyinka)”

‘Indigo women are waiting
For their men across the river’, said
The playwright to the colonel
Who would rule a republic,
And now wanted a kingdom
As hostage in a desperate drive
To the sea. So into the bridge state
Rode the other colonel, assured
Of free board and bed by hosts
Who betrayed a brother to let
Him in but, as it turned out,

Had not the fire nor the spirit
To help him on. The rest
Is history. Except the playwright,
When picked up like a rabbit on the road
In daytime, en route to principals,
All set to proclaim another kingdom,
Swore between tears in the toilet:

A triumphant ride
Is coming in my wake
Will raise again the race,
And though my friend
Refuses me gun by his side,
With my pen I shall take
Such a grape-shot, in the end
All who read my tale,
And do not know how lucky
I am to get away
With a holding charge,
Will forget in our war
Much more than *The man died*. (“The playwright and the colonels”,
FullTide)

Invariably, the section of the poem which contains Soyinka’s supposedly disposition is couched as a form of appendix to the rest of the superseding and dominating structure. The dominating

section appears as a superintending structure sitting heavily on the succeeding section which references and represents Soyinka. In other words, Soyinka is just an insignificant minuscule under the heavy domination of the colonels who sit on him like an incubus; he is crying feebly like a chick being snatched by a hawk, making ineffectual and laughable threats of:

A triumphant ride

which he promises in

my wake

The application of the modifying possessive pronoun (my) and the nominal references also indicate a significant sequence. Thus, the list includes

my wake

my friend

my pen

my tale

all these culminating in

our war

These words are part of the tearfully sworn words used by the “the playwright” when he was ‘picked up like a rabbit’. In a subsequent section of this discourse, we intend to discuss the degenerative essence of the transitivity in the swear words applied by the reference/voice which represents Soyinka.

One can clearly observe that the significance of the manipulated indentation and line length in this poem is compared to another poem of Clark’s, “Death of a weaverbird”. In this later poem, swear words of the referenced persona (Okigbo) occurs in-text just as those of Soyinka in “The

playwright and the colonels”. However, in contrast to Soyinka’s swear words, Okigbo’s speech is not indented. In fact, one of the longest lines in the poem is contained in this section. Thus,

How can I return to sing another song?

though an interrogative, indicates a correlative to the speaker as it shows the extent and effect of his career. In all, the most significant thing here is that although this speech, just like that of Soyinka, features as the last part of the poem, it does not occur as an appendage like the former.

Pictorial (re)presentation

Another such poem by which Clark applies concretization of text in reflection of the field of discourse (or context) is “Service”. In this poem, the poet describes the culture of automatic vending of basic needs which are offered at the press of a button in developed economies. The shape of the entire poem is like a one-dimensional view of an automatic teller machine (ATM). The pictorial reflection of an ATM is so apparent that one cannot but notice the semblance. Thus, in a way, this illustrates a perfect form (instance) of the marriage of form and content exhibited in a deliberate manipulation of graphological features to relay a message.

“Service”

A dime

in the slot,

And anything

from coke to coffee

Spews down your throat,

from crackers to candy

Breaks against the enamel

wear of your teeth,

(And as TV minstrels
will have it ahead
Of the Congo
andGuernical tobacco
Enough to plant
another Garden
Now, old Moses
for whom, they say,
Manna fell in the desert,
did he push a button as this,
And who knows at what price? (“Service”, *FullTide*)

Punctuation

Clark puts punctuation to a very stylistic effect in many of his poems. Because of the pejorative intent of the poet/persona, as we shall discuss in Chapter 5 of this discourse, there is no single full-stop in the entire poem, HETM. In HETM, the only punctuations which mark demarcation of stanzas – and they are not many – are question & exclamation marks.

Clark and aversion to end of line full-stop

There seems to be a consistent aversion to end-line full-stops in Clark’s poetry. Although there frequently occurs an average of two full-stops per twelve lines in a majority of Clark’s poem, it is evident that in most cases the poet applies other punctuation marks such as semi-colon, colon,

comma and elliptical marks rather than interrupt the flow of his thought often rendered in a spill or run-on-line. Sometimes, there is a deductible justification for the sparse application of full-stops, at other times, there seems to be no corresponding or comparative reason why the text should contain less or more full-stops as should have been expected. Below are, however, some foregrounded application which may be matched with the context of the text.

“His Excellency the Masquerader” (HETM) and non-deployment of the full-stop

Not a single full-stop is used in HETM. Rather than apply the full-stop to demarcate sections which one may regard as definite and autonomous sentences, the poet applies elliptical marks to indicate that something was to be said that had not been said. The exclamation mark which features as the most frequent of all the punctuations is the first and the last to be applied. This can be seen in the excerpts (first and last stanzas) below:

First Stanza

He serves
To ford between swamp and sand,
He serves!

Last Stanza

The masks!
O take off the mask! And behind?
What wind! What straw!

The exclamation marks here are somewhat marked. First, an imperative rather than a declarative is applied for the purpose of exclamation.

O take off the mask! (command)

Secondly, in the subsequent application of the exclamation mark, WH clauses, ordinarily used for interrogation are ended with exclamation marks. Therefore, it can be said that, functionally, the jagged punctuation of the text as illustrated in the unusual occurrence of exclamation (and question) marks indicates the speaker's attitude to the persona, "His Excellency". The existence or function of "His Excellency" commands an exclamation just as his relevance demands a question mark. In other words, the poem is, significantly (or symbolically) one big or long exclamation with which the speaker expresses his disapproval at the attendant culture of poor and ineffectual representation in the emergent federation.

Aversion to the full-stop, even in poems that do not express pejorative feelings is evident as there is not even one in Clark's first poem, "For granny". At the first point in which the full-stop should be applied, the poet employs a colon:

You with a start strained me to your breast: (line 6)

Subsequently, clause/sentence endings are marked with question marks as the poem ends in two interrogatives:

Did you... (line 7)

Then recognize...?

and

Or was it...? (line 14)

The next poem, second poem in *Full Tide*, is "Abiku". In "Abiku", Clark uses the full-stops. There are six periods (full-stops) in the single stanza poem. One of the periods occurs medially

while the rest are line-end periods. Somehow, the unusual preponderance of full-stops may be justified considering the fact the topic being treated is recurrent transition (birth, death and rebirth). Thus, the reference, *Abiku*, comes and goes; its life begins and ends in short spans of existence. The poem also comes with a good dose of commas, thirteen in all, averaging two per line.

“The water maid”, a poem much like “Olokun” in content, comes with just a single full-stop which marks the last word. Although relatively short and consisting in a single stanza, the dearth of punctuation (in fact, there is not a single comma or other such marks) can be justified on the basis of the fact that the speaker is in a state of near-hysteria, an anxious state requiring and demanding an urgent intervention. It is a one sentence prayer expressing a desire, an unambiguous request that commands an urgent attention, otherwise, as the lines end:

I shall dry

Shall instant die.

It is noteworthy that Modality reinforces text, as the modal feature expresses inclination and certainty signifying threat more than potentiality or disposition. The speaker thus, threatens to die; it is certain that he would die because “shall” is a modal form that carries a greater weight akin to an oath than its counterpart “will”.

Like “Abiku”, “Casualties” is another such poem that comparatively features many full-stops. Just like “Abiku”, “Casualties” deals with death or fatality. Thus, beyond the frequent periods signifying or corresponding to intermittent burst of war machines registered in the context of war, the poem expresses an end to the hitherto peaceful existence enjoyed by the warring factions. There are ten full-stops in all. However, a majority of the full-stops are contained in the

first half of the poem, that is, the first three stanzas that actually recount the experiences of killings and deaths. Thus, there is an average of three full-stops per stanza in the first section. Each of these stanzas contain either eight (stanza 1) or nine (stanzas 2 & 3) lines. Incidentally, the last section which is twice in line length to the size of the first stanza contains only one full-stop. This might be attributed to the fact that in this section, the aftermath of death and destruction are featured rather than the events that mark death and destruction. Thus, functionally, the rapid/accelerated destruction does not make room for stops. Things have fallen apart and there is destruction and disintegration.

Clark's Phono-stylistics: Rhyme and rhyme scheme

Apart from a few works, and this is especially with regard to his earliest works, Clark does not employ end rhymes as a stylistic feature. Thus, a greater percentage of the writer's poetry is written in unrhymed but sometimes rhythmic free verse. The justification of the sudden drop of the end rhyme forms might be related to the criticism Clark and other contemporaries received from Chinweizu et al (1975). These critics condemned the wholesome adoption of western canon in the classification and practice of African literature. In this regard, quite few of Clark's poetry have end rhymes. The notable ones among these include: "Fulani cattle", "The imprisonment of Obatala", "Girl birthing", "Night rain", "The water maid", "Hand over head", "Pub song", "Tide wash", "Return of the fisherman", and "Streamside exchange".

Apart from Chinweizu et al, Adetugbo (1971) accuses Clark of engaging in an artificial selection of words because of the desire to achieve a rhyming effect. This observation, though relatively valid, does not illustrate Clark's attitude to end rhymes. To an extent, Clark only employed a semblance of end rhyme in some of his earliest collection of poems. One tends to classify the rhyme scheme as a semblance because Clark's rhymes, at this and in fact other stages of his

career as a poet, can at best be described as non-systematic. We use the qualification, non-systematic because the rhyme schemes present no consistent pattern that could be easily classified. Sometimes, a single poem displays the adoption of a combination of alternate and couplet rhymes. At other times, rhyming may be reserved till the last few lines or dropped after the first few lines. Among the first twenty five poems, representing collections from Clark's earliest poetry, *Poems*, about ten (representing seventy five percent) are reflective of this non-systematic rhyme pattern. Others, including the first poem ("For granny") and the last among this earliest collection, do not show any pretense of an end rhyme. The rhyming pattern is also described as *non-systematic* because usually non-rhyming words occur at what seem to be unpredictable intervals. Moreover, the first few lines, especially lines one to four, may begin in an alternate or couplet rhymes, while the succeeding ones adopt a different pattern of rhyming. This observation can be verified in the poems below:

"Fulani cattle"

Contrition twines me like a **snake**

Each time I come upon the **wake**

Of your clan,

Undulating along in agony,

Your face a stool for mystery

What secret hope or **knowledge**,

Locked in your hump away from **man**,

Imbues you with **courage**

So mute and fierce and **wan**... ("Fulani cattle", *FullTide*)

“The imprisonment of Obatala”

The stick-insect figures! They rock the **dance**
Of snakes, dart after Him daddy-long arms,
Tangle their loping strides to mangrove **stance**,
And He, roped in the tightening pit of alarms,
Dangles in His front, full **length**,
Invincible limbs cramped by love of their **strength**.

And that mischievous stir, late sown or **spilt**
On the way between homestead and stream,
Wells up in pots long stagnant on **stilt**,
Brimms out to where ancestral eyes gleam
Till angry waves dam His **track**

And caterpillars riding out of froth break their **back**. (“The imprisonment of Obatala”, *FullTide*)

Quite essentially inconsistent as we have observed, and different from most of the first few poems in *FullTide*, “The imprisonment of Obatala” maintains a consistency in rhyme pattern till the last stanza. Thus, each stanza begins in an alternate rhyme and ends in a couplet. Its rhyme scheme, in the three stanzas of the poem which consist in a sestet each, is abab cc, de deff, ghgh ii

“Girl birthing”

Her basket of cassava, set away from **reach**

Of a log basking smooth on the **beach**,

She wades gingerly up to her **high**

Girdled hips, her underskirt lapping each **thigh**

Like calyces a corn. And as she **ducks**

Under, with deft fingers **plucks**

Loose her hair, and in their place set once *more*

The unguent flow of her limbs, the **fresh**

Warm smell of her **flesh**. (“Girl bathing”, *FullTide*)

In “Girl birthing”, as can be seen above, the rhyming pattern is different from that in “The imprisonment of Obatala” because, unlike the latter, it begins and ends in a couplet rhyme scheme. The only consistent feature of these rhyming schemes is that a greater number of them (if not all) end in a couplet. Sometimes they are heroic couplet; at other times they are not.

Initial word rhyme

“Streamside exchange” represents one of the most significant poems of Clark. The poem is very significant because it has received a very wide range of evaluation and criticism compared to all (any) other poems by the poet. Moreover, the poem, having undergone what Clark calls a “cosmetic surgery” offers a veritable illustration for some of the essential discoveries we have made in Clark’s poetry.

Critics are of the general opinion that a great deal of artistry was employed in the crafting of this poem. Maduka (1984), Nwoga and Vincent & Senanu agree that the poem is simple without being simplistic. In other words, its simplicity is in the deployment of basic linguistic features; however, the arrangement of these simple features imbues the text with an apparent complexity as well as depth of meaning that has a universal appeal. It is therefore not a surprise that of all Clark's poems, this is the only work that shows the special feature of an initial word rhyme or *rhymematching* in the first six lines of the poem. In other words, as the terminal words show a rhyming scheme so do the initial words. In this regard, the initial words as listed below present a special rhyming scheme:

River (R) a	River (R) a	A (A) d
Sitting (S) b	Sing (S) b	Will (W) e
On (O) c	Of (O) c	(abc, abc, de)

In the same vein, the last part, which is the bird's response, completes the special rhyme scheme in:

You (Y) **f**

And (A) **d**

Tide (T) **g**

And (A) **d**

(fdgd)

Rhyming of sequential lexical features

A special kind of rhyme involving rhythmic similarity between structures, especially nominal and verbal features, can be observed in some of Clark's poems. Such lexical similarity in sound and rhythm occurs in "The masquerade". It is one of those poems which feature the mask motif. However, unlike a greater percentage of these other poems that also feature the mask motif, "The masquerade" indicates a comparatively positive disposition of the poet to a recognized cultural feature of his people. Compared to its counterpart, "His Excellency, the masquerader" (HETM), "The masquerade" presents a careful combination of linguistic forms especially with regard to lexico-grammar, as our subsequent analysis would testify.

"The masquerade"

The shark masquerade, at that stage
When he could **cutup** his on mother, had
The whole town running for cover,
Many taking fast to their boats, and
Young women all out ululating when
From the corner of my eye, which one
I cannot tell now, I found the shark masquerade
At my back. Although I ran harder than
I had ever done at school for first place,
Believing in my racing heart I was
On eagle wings, his quick loping strides

Soon **lapped up** the space between us
And just when all the crowd and I thought
His cutlass had **come down** on me,
The shark masquerade **stooped down**
And **picked me up** in his arms, all there
Shouting in disbelief, ‘The Shark Masquerade
Is carrying Pepper in his arms!’ And so he did,
Dancing quite some distance with me
In his arms, which seemed to last the whole day,
Before **setting me down**, like a piece of porcelain,
While town and river gave cheers with one voice,
As only heard for masquerades straight from the sea. (“The masquerade”, *FullTide*)

(a) cut up (a)

(b) lapped up (a)

(a) come down (b)

(c) stooped down (b)

(d) picked (me) up (a)

(c) setting (me) down (b)

Here, in a special rhyming of these phrasal verbs, the initial word rhyme indicates a rhyme pattern/scheme of **aba, cdc** while the terminal words are rhymed **aa, bb, ab**. Although what is

observed above can be said to be an arbitrary and unmotivated feature, however, it cannot be taken for granted more so that this particular poem is one of those which express special cultural affinity or attachment between the poet/persona and the referent quite unlike in HETM where the poet castigates and casts aspersion on the subject. The “Shark masquerade” which everyone dreads because of its awe-inspiring and violence-threatening disposition is hereby relayed as a benevolent and friendly personality who does such an extraordinary thing as “picking Pepper up in his arms”. Therefore, if the poet decides to involve an extraordinary artistry in recapturing the event, it is no wonder.

In “One country”, this similarity of sound in lexical pattering also occurs. Here, applying transitivity with regard to lexical/nominal forms, Clark draws attention to the dire environmental and social degradation in the Niger Delta.

their tenements

Their settlements

their nights

their rights

Although these features do not occur as line-ending forms, they are sequentially applied and offer a synchronic patterning that is quite significant. Another significant aspect of the transitivity deployed in this sequence is the contrast and contradiction existing among the nominal forms: *tenements*, *settlements* and *rights*. Thus, the minority aborigines dwell in their natural *settlements* under a *tenement* condition indicating that their *rights* have been denied them. A *tenement* unlike a *settlement* implies that they dwell on the land not as actual owners but as tenants who have been dispossessed by the overbearing majority to whose benefit the idea of “One country” is quite understandable.

Such similar parallelism of syntactic and phonological forms, though this is more like parallelism, is also evident in “Party song”. Here, the first stanza of the poem indicates initial and end-rhyming features.

Here we mill drinking by midnight

Here we mill bobbing by fairylight

Here we mill glowing by dimlight (“Party song”, *FullTide*)

The paradigmatic forms which do not indicate repetition

drinking...midnight

bobbing...fairylight

glowing...dimlight

are all rhymed. In this excerpt, parallelism in structure is complimentary to parallelism in lexicosemantics. Structurally, each line of the excerpt is made up of four words. These constituent words all indicate a paradigmatic relation.

Conclusion

What is presented in this article by no means represents the entirety of graphological and phonostylistic features of J.P. Clark’s work as a poet. At best, this can only be termed a gleaning of his popular works, that is, such works that the poet is easily identified with by scholars and students alike. However, bearing in mind the popularity of the poet and the common inclination of Nigerian scholars and students towards the study of the poet, this present work is careful to avoid approaches to poetic analysis which might be considered or accused of what Eghagha (2005) sees as a “rehash” of pedestrian ideas.

As an accomplished creative writer whose career spans more than six decades, beginning around 1955 at the University College, Ibadan, J.P. Clark has had his name registered a poet of repute by carving significant niche for himself in the creative use of the English language. Clark's success in the application of special linguistic forms to relay messages that bear connections to his Nigerian, nay, African, context and milieu is evinced in his numerous poetic works. The stylistic application of rhyming forms and the special deployment of graphology in his poems help to enhance their meaning/message potential and signification.

Special end-line rhyme schemes as well as distinctive lexical forms that indicate paradigmatic relations are some peculiar styles which Clark's poetry, as analyzed in this research, has revealed. With respect to graphology, Clark has demonstrated a fusion of form and content in order to derive semiotic reference that enhances his thematic concern.

This paper, besides presenting an analysis of J.P. Clark's poetry, has shown how literature as an aesthetic form can be explicated and its semiotics made accessible to readers and learners alike, based on the examination of the phonological and graphological levels of linguistics.

References

Adetugbo, A. (1971). Form and style. In G. Moore (Ed.), *Modern African writers* (pp. xx–xx). Lagos: Unilag and Evans Publishers.

Anozie, S. (1989). *Structural models and African poetics*. London: Routledge.

Chinweizu, J., Jemie, O., & Madubuike, I. (1975). *Towards the decolonization of African literature* (Vol. 1). Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers.

Clark, J. P. (2010). *Full tide*. Ibadan: Mosuro.

Crystal, D. and Davy D. (1969), *Investigating English style*. London: Longman
Eghagha, H. (2004). Unmasking the masquerade and extending the canon of Nigerian literature. In S. Awonusi & E. A. Babalola (Eds.), *The domestication of English in Nigeria* (pp. 480–497). Lagos: University of Lagos Press.

Halliday M.A.K & Matthiessen C. (2004). *An introduction to functional grammar*, London: Edward Anold.

Maduka, C. (1984). *Across frontiers: Comparative literature and national integration*. University of Port Harcourt Inaugural Lecture Series, No. 14.

McCarthy, M, Matthiessen, C.M.I.M. & Slade, D. (2010); ‘Discourse Analysis’ in Schmitt, Norbert, *An Introduction to Applied Linguistics*, United Kingdom: Arnold.

Nwoga, D. (2005). *West African verse: An anthology*. London: Longman.

Okai, A. (2011). Casualties of the womb and writers as murderers of the gods – The creational marathon of J. P. Clark-Bekederemo. In S. E. Ododo & G. Mbajiorgu (Eds.), *Songs of gold: Fresh perspectives on Clark-Bekederemo* (pp. 29–41).

Vincent, T., & Senanu, K. E. (2005). *A selection of African poetry*. London: Longman.

Yeibo, E. (2011). Group types as style markers in J. P. Clark-Bekederemo's poetry. In S. E. Ododo & G. Mbajiorgu (Eds.), *Songs of gold: Fresh perspectives on Clark-Bekederemo* (pp. 202–218).

Yerima, A. (2011). Contending with Clark-Bekederemo's fluid creative complexity. In S. E. Ododo & G. Mbajiorgu (Eds.), *Songs of gold: Fresh perspectives on Clark-Bekederemo* (pp. 23–28).